

ESCAPE - Connecting ESFRI to EOSC

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EOSC Services, Collaborations and RDA
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The European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle Physics ESFRI Research Infrastructures

EOSC and ESFRI Science Communities

WP4
Virtual Observatories

WP3
Software devel. and repos.

The European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle Physics ESFRI Research Infrastructures

- **Multi Messenger Astronomy**

- **Radio**

- SKA (Square Kilometre Array)
- JIVE VLBI (Very large Baseline Instrument)

- **Visible Light**

- European Extreme Large Telescope (ELT)
- European Solar Telescope (EST)

- **Gamma Rays**

- CTA

- **Cosmic Rays: Neutrinos**

- KM3Net

- **Gravitational Waves**

- EGO-VIRGO

- **High Energy Physics**

- **HL-LHC**

- High Energy Particle

- **FAIR**

- High density exotic matter physics

International Virtual Observatory Alliance

Gathering and coordinating the **European contributions** to the Virtual Observatory (see also next slide).

Supporting the actors with community actions:

→ **Data Providers, VO developers, Science Users.**

Continuing impact for “all-sky” astronomy.

The Virtual Observatory (VO) is the vision that **astronomical datasets and other resources should work as a seamless whole.**

The IVOA is an **organisation that debates and agrees the technical standards** that are needed to make the VO possible.

IVOA FAIR Architecture

LEVEL 0
LEVEL 1

Genova et al. 2015

Connecting ESFRI projects to EOSC through VO framework CEVO (WP4)

- Connect the ESFRI and other astronomy RI to the EOSC through the VO framework
- Refine and further implement FAIR principles for astronomy data through common standards for interoperability
- Establish data stewardship practices to add value to the scientific content of ESFRI data archives

Storage, computing, applications...

- **WP2 DIOS**
 - Contribute to the **federation of global EOSC resources** through an implementation of the Data-Lake concept to **manage extremely large volumes of data** up to the multi-exabyte scale
- **WP3 OSSR**
 - **Support for "scientific software"** as a major component of the ESFR-RI “data” to be stored and displayed **in EOSC** via dedicated **community-based catalogues**
- **WP5 ESAP**
 - Implementation of **scientific analysis platforms enabling EOSC researchers** to organize data collections, analyse them, access ESFRI's software tools, and provide their own customized workflows

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Interoperability of these goals connected to CEVO activities!

